

Bacteriocinogenic Potential of Crude Extract from Lactic Acid Bacteria Obtained from Selected Fermented Food Samples Against Some Foodborne Pathogenic Bacteria

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Abstract

The roles of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) in inhibition of pathogenic organisms have opened new horizons in the fields of medical science and food biotechnology. Members of lactic acid bacteria are known to have antimicrobial properties due to their ability to produce bacteriocins and organic acids. This study was designed to assess some locally fermented food as potential sources of LABs and to assess the bacteriocinogenic efficacy of their crude bacteriocins against foodborne pathogenic bacteria. LABs were isolated from fermented pineapple juice, "nunu", "ogi", cheese and yogurt using pour plate method on de Man Rogosa Sharpe (MRS) agar. Characterization and identification of isolates were done through standard microbiological methods. Cell free supernatants (CFS) from de Man Rogosa Sharpe (MRS) broth cultures of the LAB strains were used as crude bacteriocin and screened for bacteriocinogenic action on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by agar well diffusion method. The total bacterial count ranged from $1.15 \pm 0.12 \times 10^2$ in yoghurt to $3.87 \pm 0.05 \times 10^2$ CFU/ml in "nunu". Isolated LABs were identified as *Lactococcus* sp., *Lactobacillus* spp., *Streptococcus* sp. and *Leuconostoc* sp. The crude bacteriocin obtained from LABs isolated from yoghurt and cheese had an inhibitory effect on *Escherichia coli* with a diameter of 12.67 ± 1.16 mm and 14.67 ± 0.58 mm respectively while crude bacteriocin obtained from *Lactococcus* sp and *Streptococcus* sp (pineapple juice) had inhibitory effect against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with a diameter of 13.67 ± 0.58 mm and 14.00 ± 0.00 mm respectively. There was no inhibitory effect against *Staphylococcus aureus*. This study revealed the bacteriocinogenic potential of crude bacteriocin obtained from isolated LABs on some foodborne pathogens tested.

Keywords: Bacteriocin, Lactic acid bacteria, Foodborne pathogens, pathogenic bacteria

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Introduction

One of the most well-known probiotics is lactic acid bacteria, which has been shown to be a beneficial addition to diet that significantly improves health and vitality. The probiotic potential of lactic acid bacteria and their function in suppressing pathogenic organisms have opened new avenues for research in the realms of food biotechnology and medicine in recent decades. The application of lactic acid bacteria has been justified by developments in the field of microbiology. Research in fields like microbiology, physiology, genetics, and more recently,

genomics, has advanced due to the industrial significance of lactic acid bacteria (Mozzi et al., 2010).

Fruit is a part of our daily consumption. Globally, it is consistently incorporated into dietary regimens as whole fruit juice, beverages, or still drinks. The world consumed 117.7 billion gallons of industrialized still drinks. 77% of the total volume was consumed in 40 nations, with 23.5 million liters falling into the juice category, 42 million into the still drink category, and 35 million into the powdered and concentrated juice or still drink category, etc. (Mortuza, 2016). A fruit is a

structural component of a plant that contains seeds. Mangoes, oranges, grapes, and other fruits are examples of fruits that are often fleshy, sweet, and edible when fresh. They are ripened ovaries or carpels that contain seed. Fruits are like vegetables, they are composed of a variety of the phytochemical components, a high-water content (85% on average), a little amount of fat, protein, and carbohydrates (starch and cellulose).

Recent studies have substantiated the antimicrobial efficacy of crude bacteriocins derived from lactic acid bacteria (LAB) isolated from fermented foods. For instance, research carried out by Usman (2023) demonstrated that crude bacteriocins produced by *Lactobacillus* species isolated from "Nono," a traditional Nigerian fermented milk, demonstrated a strong antibacterial effect against pathogens such as *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. These findings underscore the potential of LAB-derived bacteriocins as organic bio-preservatives to extend the shelf life and safety of food.

Yogurt has been used as a medicinal ingredient in the Ayurvedic medical tradition in India since ancient times. In recent years a bunch of study is being performed on the health benefit of yogurt. It is important for public awareness upgradation of health through the implications of yoghurt in the daily diet as a natural probiotic, food and medicine. Originally, the word "yoghurt" was Turkish. It refers to a coagulated or curdled milk product that is the outcome of bacterial fermentation. Yogurt cultures are bacteria that convert lactose to lactic acid and transform milk proteins into unique textures and nutrients.

Due to their functional and sensory qualities, maize, grains, sorghum, and millets were known to be key cereals for making pap (Achi and Ukwuru, 2015). Most food production, including "tuwo," typically uses the yellow and white color maize varieties, which have been found to be high in vitamin A and sugar, respectively (Ijarotimi and Kenshinro, 2012). It has been noted that adding legumes to maize, such as cowpea, amabambara nut, and soybean, greatly improves the protein composition of meals based on cereal (Terefe, et al., 2021).

Lactic acid bacteria are widely known for their ability to synthesize a wide range of metabolites that favorably change the fermented food products' nutritional, sensory, and technical attributes, as well as the production of lactic acid as the main byproduct of their anaerobic metabolism. Lactic acid bacteria have been used extensively as probiotics, starter cultures, and in

the manufacture of compounds (i.e., nutraceuticals) due to their versatile metabolism. (Naeem et al., 2012; Emerenini et al., 2013; Ruiz Rodriguez et al., 2017). This study was therefore aimed at determining the bacteriocinogenic potential of crude bacteriocin obtained from lactic acid bacteria isolated from some fermented food against selected foodborne pathogens

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

Pineapple fruits, Yoghurt, Cheese, Nunu and Ogi were purchased at Ipata market Ilorin, Kwara State Nigeria. The samples were packed in sterile sampling bags and taken to the Central research laboratory, Tanke, Ilorin.

Collection of Foodborne Pathogens

The food pathogenic organisms were isolated through subculturing from existing plates in Laboratory from the Department of Microbiology, University of Ilorin. This involves selecting colonies of interest from agar plates that have been previously inoculated with food samples. Using sterile techniques, a loop was used to transfer a small amount of the colony to a new sterile culture medium, allowing the pathogens to grow in a controlled environment samples in the laboratory. Once isolated, the cultures were transferred into sterile, leak-proof containers to prevent contamination. Each container was clearly labeled with essential information, such as the type of organism, date of collection. It was then transported to Central Laboratory, Tanke, Ilorin for further analysis.

Isolation of Pure Bacteria Colonies

Isolation of pure bacteria colonies was done using serial dilution and pour plate techniques. Distilled water was used to wash and rinse the McCartney bottles. After adding 9 milliliters of distilled water to each bottle, they were then sterilized in an autoclave at 121 °C for 15 mins. After sterilization, the bottles were allowed to cool, 5 bottles were designated for each of the samples; pineapple juice, yoghurt, cheese, nunu and ogi with each bottle labelled 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} respectively. One (1) ml of each of the samples was withdrawn and dispensed into the first bottle designated for each sample and homogenized thoroughly. Afterwards, 1 ml was withdrawn from the first bottle and transferred into the second bottle, the same procedure was repeated for the McCartney bottle 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} . One (1) ml of the diluents from each of the bottles for the 5 samples was inoculated into sterile Petri plates and

sterilized media was poured into them. They were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Due to mixed growth colonies on the plates, a close observation of morphological characterization of distinct pure colonies was made. Distinct colonies were subcultured onto freshly prepared media plates. Slants were used to maintain pure colonies for further study (Eni, 2010; Makinde et al., 2020).

Morphological and Biochemical Characterization of Isolates

Sterile plates were filled with de Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe broth (MRS) media, which was then allowed to solidify. The agar plates were streaked using aseptic technique by selecting a loopful of a 24-hour-old pure culture with an inoculating loop using the three-quadrant streak plate method. The plates were subsequently placed in an incubator at 37 °C for a duration of 24 hours. Following incubation, the bacterial growth patterns were examined for gram reaction, size, color, elevation, opacity, shape and texture (Deshmukh et al., 2020). Isolates obtained were further characterized morphologically using the colonial morphology and cell wall reaction to Gram staining. Biochemical characterization such as Indole, MR-VP, Catalase, Coagulase, Oxidase and Sugar Fermentation test) were also carried out using procedures described by Makinde et al. (2020).

Bacteriocin Preparation for Antibacterial Activity Testing

Extraction of antibacterial compound from LAB: To produce crude extracts, submerged state

fermentation was applied to active LAB strains. Cell-free culture supernatant (CFS) was extracted from each sample by centrifuging it for 15 minutes at 4°C at 6,000 rpm after incubation. Ammonium sulfate was combined with the resulting cell-free solution (saturation level 70%). At 4°C for two hours, a 250-rpm rotary shaker was used to shake the mixture. Ultimately, a separating funnel was used to separate the organic phase from the aqueous phase, and a rotary vacuum concentrator was used to concentrate the mixture to dryness (Islam et al., 2020).

Determination of Antibacterial Activity

A volume of 100 µl of the cell-free supernatant was added to a well (6 mm in diameter) bored in Mueller Hinton agar, which had already been seeded with a 0.5 MacFarland standard of strains, (10^8 CFU/ml). The zones of inhibition (mm) were then measured to assess antibacterial activity on the culture plates after a 24-hour incubation period at 37 °C (Adetoye et al., 2018).

Results and Discussions

This study revealed the presence of Lactic Acid Bacteria in Pineapple fruits, Yogurt, Cheese, Nunu and Ogi.

Lactic Acid Bacteria Count

The total Lactic Acid Bacteria count from the samples is presented in Table 1. The yoghurt sample had a count of $1.15 \pm 0.21 \times 10^2$ CFU/ml indicating the lowest count and Nunu sample with highest count of $3.87 \pm 0.05 \times 10^2$ CFU/ml.

Table 1: Lactic Acid Bacterial Count Obtained from Selected Samples

Samples	Bacterial count (10^2 Cfu/ml)
Ogi	2.33 ± 0.53^b
Pineapple Juice	$3.17 \pm 0.59^{a, b}$
Yoghurt	1.15 ± 0.21^c
Nunu	3.87 ± 0.05^a
Cheese	3.63 ± 0.15^a

Values are means (n=2) \pm SD. Values bearing the same superscript are not significantly different from each other (P < 0.05)

Morphological and Biochemical Characterization of the Lactic Acid Bacteria

All isolates were Gram positive, Entire and Non-sporing other characterization include; elevation, color, and shape (Table 2). *Lactococcus* sp and *Streptococcus thermophilus* were isolated from Pineapple juice, *Lactobacillus* sp. was isolated from Ogi and Nunu, from Cheese – *Leuconostoc* sp. and

Lactobacillus sp., were isolated (Table 3). The Bacteriocinogenic Lactic Acid Bacteria which were isolated and identified from indigenous Cheese, Yoghurt, Nunu, Pineapple and Ogi conforms to the characteristics of a typical LAB as shown by the colonial morphology and biochemical behaviour. Utilizing multiple Lactic Acid Bacteria combined with bacteriocin as a means of biopreservative might have significant uses in enhancing food safety.

Table 2: Morphological Characterization and Gram Reaction of the Lactic Acid Bacteria

Bacteria isolates	Shape	Colour	Gram Reaction	Elevation	Spore Staining	Margin
P2	Cocci	White	+	Raised	-	Entire
P1	Cocci	Yellow	+	Flat	-	Entire
N1	Rod	Off-white	+	Raised	-	Entire
N2	Rod	White	+	Convex	-	Entire
Y	Rod	Off-white	+	Raised	-	Entire
C1	Rod	Pale yellow	+	Raised	-	Entire
C2	Cocci	White	+	Raised	-	Entire
O	Rod	White	+	Flat	-	Entire

Keys: P - Pineapple, juice N - Nunu, C - Cheese, O - Ogi, Y – Yoghurt,

Antibacterial Activities of Bacteriocin Obtained from LAB against Selected Pathogenic Organisms

The crude bacteriocin of LABs obtained from yoghurt and cheese had an inhibitory effect on *Escherichia coli* with a diameter of 12.67 ± 1.16 mm and 14.67 ± 0.58 mm respectively while crude bacteriocin obtained from *Lactococcus* sp and *Streptococcus* sp (pineapple juice) had inhibitory effect against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with a diameter of 13.67 ± 0.58 mm and 14.00 ± 0.00 mm respectively. Crude bacteriocin obtained from *Leuconostoc* sp (cheese) had no inhibitory effect on the three test organisms. There was no inhibitory effect against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Table 3: Biochemical Characterization of the Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolates

Bacteria	In	Ox	Ca	Co	MR	Sugar Fermentation					Probable Isolates Organisms
						Glu	Suc	Lac	Mal	Fru	
P2	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	<i>Lactococcus</i> sp.
P1	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Streptococcus</i> sp.
N1	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.
N2	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.
Y	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.
C1	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.
C2	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Leuconostoc</i> sp.
O	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.

KEYS: P- Pineapple

N- Nunu

C- Cheese

O- Ogi

In- Indole

Ox- Oxidase

Ca- Catalase

Co- Coagulase

Glu- Glucose

Suc-Sucrose

Lac- Lactose

Mal- Maltose

Y- Yogurt

MR- Methyl Red

Fru- Fructose

Table 4: Antibacterial Activities of Bacteriocin Obtained from LAB against Selected Pathogenic Organisms

Bacteria Isolates	Test organisms [Zone of inhibition (mm)]		
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
<i>Lactococcus</i> sp.(P2)	0 ^c	0	13.67 ± 0.58 ^a
<i>Streptococcus</i> sp.(P1)	0 ^c	0	14.00 ± 0.00 ^a
<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.(N2)	0 ^c	0	13.33 ± 0.58 ^{a, b}
<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.(Y)	12.67 ± 1.16 ^b	0	0 ^d
<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.(C1)	14.67 ± 0.58 ^a	0	12.33 ± 0.58 ^c
<i>Leuconostoc</i> sp. (C2)	0 ^c	0	0 ^d
<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.(O)	0 ^c	0	13.33 ± 0.58 ^{a, b}

Values are means (n=3) ± SD. Values bearing the same superscript down the column are

Keys: P - Pineapple, juice N - Nunu, C - Cheese, O - Ogi, Y – Yoghurt,

Discussion

The current study focused on the bacteriocinogenic activity of crude bacteriocin produced by lactic acid bacteria from selected fermented food samples against some foodborne pathogenic bacteria. In the present investigation, five samples were used (pineapple juice, yoghurt, cheese, nunu and ogi).

The lactic acid bacterial counts from the various fermented food/beverage indicated that the samples are rich in lactic acid bacteria which can be utilized for production of metabolites; this can be harnessed for various activities against foodborne pathogens. These results are consistent with earlier studies that demonstrate the diversity of lactic acid bacteria in various fermented foods. A study by Olasupo et al. (2018), for example, found comparable numbers of lactic acid bacteria in conventional fermented meals, highlighting the significance of raw ingredients and fermentation conditions in bacterial population determination.

According to Omoregie et al. (2020), the fermentation processes and microbial populations involved may also be responsible for the higher numbers in nunu and cheese. However, as Tamang et al. (2016) highlighted, the lower numbers in yoghurt may be attributable to the starting cultures utilized.

The morphological characterization and Gram reaction of the bacterial isolates from different food/beverage samples, revealed that they all had attributes of Lactic acid Bacteria. However, the color variations of the LABs might be a sign of changes in development circumstances or metabolic activity (Tamang et al., 2016).

Lactobacillus's role in fermentation processes is highlighted by its consistent presence in a variety of samples (Olasupo et al., 2018). Furthermore, *Leuconostoc* sp., which is recognized for its function in the fermentation of dairy and vegetable products (Omoregie et al., 2020) was also obtained. Ultimately, findings from this study demonstrate the diversity of lactic acid bacteria present in fermented foods, which are critical for flavor development, preservation and bacteriocinogenic activity amongst others.

This observation aligns with findings by Oyedokun et al. (2023), who stated that identical biochemical traits, such as catalase negativity and acid generation, were shared by

LAB strains isolated from fermented yogurt from Nigeria. Furthermore, using locally fermented foods, Uzoh et al. (2022) highlighted LAB species as *Lactococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Pediococcus*, and *Lactobacillus*, noting their negative responses to catalase and oxidase tests, which are characteristic features of LAB.

The ability of the LABs to ferment carbohydrates for lactic acid production ascertains their usefulness in the fermentation of food. Ayodeji et al. (2021), described LAB from fermented sorghum and maize products, emphasizing their varied sugar fermentation capacities and possible use for different purposes. Furthermore, the diversity of LAB in Nigerian fermented foods and their important involvement in food fermentation processes were highlighted by Adesemoye et al. (2025).

The antibacterial properties of bacteriocins derived from different lactic acid bacteria (LAB) showed a great deal of variation against the test organisms.

Crude bacteriocin obtained from *Lactobacillus* sp. isolated from pineapple juice samples showed no inhibitory effect against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. However, it exhibits significant antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, this may be as a result of the specific mechanism of action of the bacteriocin directly affecting the cell membrane components or metabolic pathways unique to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, as well as its susceptibility to the bacteriocin's mode of inhibition (Sarikhani et al., 2020 and Wang et al., 2022).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa was inhibited by the crude bacteriocin acquired from *Lactococcus* sp and *Streptococcus* sp. obtained from pineapple juice while *Lactobacillus* sp. from cheese, nunu and ogi also showed considerable suppression (Ogunbanwo et al., 2003; Sharma et al., 2023).

These findings align with previous research indicating that certain *Lactobacillus* sp. possess strong antibacterial properties against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Alemayehu et al., 2020). In contrast, crude bacteriocin from *Leuconostoc* sp. demonstrated no inhibition against any of the foodborne pathogens tested, which is in line with prior research that found this genus to have weak antibacterial activity (Thapa and Basnet, 2015).

The bacteriocinogenic potential of the LAB strains emphasizes how crucial strain selection

is for antibacterial activities. Future research should focus on characterizing the specific bacteriocins that these strains produce and elucidating their mechanisms of action to better understand their potential applications as natural antibacterial agents.

Conclusion

In the study, it was revealed that lactic acid bacteria isolated from pineapple juice, nunu, cheese, yoghurt and ogi had bacteriocinogenic activity against some of the foodborne pathogens.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the support of the Central research lab, Tanke and the Microbiology Department Laboratory at Kwara State University, Malete, for providing the necessary laboratory equipment and materials that enabled this study.

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